

KONFRONTÁCIA AKO DŔKAZNÝ PROSTRIEDOK

CONFRONTATION AS A MEANS OF PROOF

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Annotation: *In this scientific study, the author draws on the findings of the completed international scientific research project conducted at the Academy of the Police Force in Bratislava, entitled "Confrontation in Criminalistics Theory and Practice" (Výsk. 247), and emphasizes the importance of applying criminalistics-tactical recommendations in the investigative process. The study also analyses the differences between the Slovak Republic and the Czech Republic in terms of the preparation of investigators and authorized officers, their willingness to engage in further education, and the application of psychological knowledge in the performance of this investigative act.*

Keywords: *confrontation, evidence, tactics, preparation*

Prior to the adoption of the recodified Code of Criminal Procedure (Act No. 301/2005 Coll.), confrontation as an independent means of evidence did not exist in Slovak criminal law. Nevertheless, it was commonly applied in investigative practice, with its legal basis derived from the provisions of the older Code of Criminal Procedure — specifically § 94(1) of Act No. 141/1961 Coll. governing the examination of the accused, and § 103 of the same act governing the examination of a witness. Section 94(1) itself permitted placing the accused "face to face" with a witness or co-accused in situations where their statements diverged on material points and this discrepancy could not be resolved by other means. Confrontation therefore had no independent legal regulation and was legally subsumed under the institution of examination.¹ Pursuant to § 103 of Act No. 141/1961 Coll., it was stated that "The provisions of § 93(1) and (2), § 94, and § 95 on the examination of the accused shall apply mutatis mutandis to the examination of a witness."²

In the early 1980s, there was significant disagreement among experts in the fields of criminalistics and criminal law regarding the nature and status of confrontation. One group advocated for its codification as an independent means of evidence in the Code of Criminal Procedure, even though it was not expressly regulated therein. A second, procedurally oriented group considered this step unnecessary, viewing confrontation merely as a special form of examination. In practice, however, confrontation was commonly conducted — not only in judicial proceedings but also during preliminary investigations, where the entire act was recorded in a confrontation protocol. This gave rise to a characteristic discrepancy between the de facto situation and the de lege lata position: in practice, confrontation functioned as an independent procedural act, yet legally it remained subsumed under the institution of examination. The professional and legal community accepted that confrontation was carried out in practice beyond the literal wording of the law — that is, not only between the accused and a witness, or between co-accused, but also between witnesses themselves and in other combinations.³

¹ § 94 ods. 1 zákona č. 141/1961 Sb. Trestný poriadok v znení neskorších predpisov.

² § 103 zákona č. 141/1961 Sb. Trestný poriadok v znení neskorších predpisov.

³ LACA, M. Komparácia využívania konfrontácie vo vybraných krajinách európskej únie. In *Právni rozpravy 2016, Mezinárodní vědecká konference oblasti práva a právních věd s podtitulem Teorie, vývoj, praxe práva*. Hradec Králové : Magnanimitas, s. 39 – 46.

Current Legal Status

Pursuant to § 119(3) of the Code of Criminal Procedure, "anything that may contribute to the proper clarification of a matter and that was obtained from means of evidence under this act or under a special act may serve as evidence. Means of evidence include in particular the examination of the accused, witnesses, experts, expert opinions and expert statements, verification of testimony on site, recognition, reconstruction, investigative experiment, inspection, items and documents relevant to criminal proceedings, notifications, and information obtained through the use of information-technology means or means of operative-investigative activity."⁴

Although § 119(3) of the Code of Criminal Procedure does not explicitly mention confrontation in this enumeration, the use of the word "in particular" clearly signals the demonstrative — rather than exhaustive — character of this list. On the basis of the introductory part of this provision, according to which "anything that may contribute to the proper clarification of a matter may serve as evidence," confrontation can be fully regarded as a means of evidence. This conclusion is further confirmed by the fact that confrontation has its own independent legal regulation in § 125 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, whereby the legislator has definitively confirmed its nature as a means of evidence de lege lata.

The current statutory text of confrontation reads as follows:

- „1. If the statement of the accused disagrees with the statement of a co-accused or a witness on significant circumstances and the discrepancy cannot be resolved otherwise, the accused may be placed face to face with that person.
2. Persons placed face to face may ask each other questions only with the consent of the examining officer.
3. The provisions of paragraphs 1 and 2 shall not apply in the case of an undercover agent, an endangered witness, a protected witness, a witness whose identity is concealed, and a witness in criminal proceedings conducted for offences of terrorism; this shall not apply in the case of an undercover agent who has consented to the disclosure of their identity.
4. The application of the provisions of paragraphs 1 and 2 is not permissible where the witness is under 18 years of age.
5. In criminal proceedings concerning offences against human dignity, the offence of ill-treatment of a close person or an entrusted person, or the offence of trafficking in human beings, the provisions of paragraphs 1 and 2 shall not apply where the witness is a person against whom such an offence was committed. The provisions of paragraphs 1 and 2 shall likewise not apply in the case of a witness against whom an offence was committed by violence or threat of violence, where there is a risk of causing secondary victimisation or repeated victimisation, having regard in particular to age, sex, sexual orientation, race, nationality, religious belief, intellectual maturity, or the relationship to or dependence on the offender."⁵

Legal and Criminalistic-Tactical Analysis of § 125 of the Code of Criminal Procedure

Procedural Legal Framework (paragraphs 1 and 2)

Pursuant to § 125(1), the Code of Criminal Procedure establishes three cumulative conditions for the admissibility of confrontation:

1. The existence of a significant discrepancy in the statements
2. The impossibility of resolving this discrepancy by other means
3. The procedural status of the persons being confronted (the accused versus a co-accused or a witness)

⁴ §119 ods. 3 z. č. 301/2005z.z. Trestný poriadok v znení neskorších predpisov.

⁵ §125 z. č. 301/2005z.z. Trestný poriadok v znení neskorších predpisov.

The law thus attributes a subsidiary character to confrontation. It is a measure of last resort, not a standard examination procedure.

Pursuant to § 125(2), the provision regulates the right of the persons placed face to face to ask each other questions, but exclusively with the consent of the examining officer, whereby the law protects the integrity of the act and the principle of active conduct of the confrontation by the investigator.

Criminalistic-Tactical Principles in the Context of § 125(1) and (2) of the Code of Criminal Procedure

From a criminalistic-tactical standpoint, the law implicitly establishes several key principles that the professional literature explicitly develops:⁶

Principle of initiative of the confronted persons — the investigator actively directs the entire course of the confrontation and is not merely a passive observer.

Principle of vigilance — the investigator must be prepared for the risk that a previously truthful statement may change to an untruthful one during the confrontation under the influence of the other person's presence.

Principle of observation — confrontation provides a unique opportunity to monitor the behaviour, reactions, and non-verbal expressions of the confronted persons, which may indicate comfort or discomfort with their statements.

Prohibition of suggestive and captious questions — this principle applies to both confronted persons, and its violation may call the entire act into question.

The law establishes several categories of persons against whom confrontation may not be used at all, or only under strictly limited conditions. The first category comprises an undercover agent, an endangered witness, a protected witness, and a witness whose identity is concealed, where the primary reason for protection is their personal safety. The sole exception to this rule is the case where the undercover agent has personally consented to the disclosure of their identity. The second category is a witness under the age of 18, where the law permits no exception and the prohibition on confrontation is absolute. The third category comprises victims of offences against human dignity, the offence of ill-treatment of a close person or an entrusted person, and the offence of trafficking in human beings. Here too, the law permits no exception. The fourth and most broadly conceived category consists of victims of any violent offences where there is a risk of secondary or repeated victimisation. In these cases, the admissibility of confrontation is assessed individually, taking into account factors such as age, sex, sexual orientation, race, nationality, religious belief, intellectual maturity, or the victim's relationship to the offender and any dependence on them.⁷

From the perspective of criminalistic tactics, the exceptions in paragraphs 3 to 5 represent a fundamental criminalistic-tactical deficit in the investigative process. In these cases, the investigator is compelled to resolve significant discrepancies exclusively by other methods, such as verification of testimony on site, expert evidence, or recognition. Particularly problematic is the category of victims of violent offences (paragraph 5, second sentence), where the law introduces individual assessment of the risk of secondary victimisation, taking into account factors such as age, sex, sexual orientation, or dependence on the offender — placing high demands on the criminalistic-psychological preparation of the investigator. The provision of § 125 of the Code of Criminal Procedure is procedurally functional and well-structured, but from a criminalistic-tactical standpoint it remains a bare legal framework. The law does not establish the order of examination of the confronted persons, does not reflect the distinction between partial and full confrontation, and does not regulate the preparatory phase of the act. The entire criminalistic-tactical methodology thus remains at the level of professional

⁶ LACA, M., *Výsluch a konfrontácia v aplikačnej praxi*. s. 74-75.

⁷ §125 ods. 3, 4, 5 z. č. 301/2005z.z. Trestný poriadok v znení neskorších predpisov.

recommendations and investigator training, which directly confirms the justification for scientific inquiry into this subject matter. An examination of confrontation as a criminalistic-tactical act would not be complete without empirical verification of how this procedural institution is applied in everyday investigative practice. Although the legal regulation contained in § 125 of the Code of Criminal Procedure provides confrontation with a normative framework, the actual effectiveness of this act depends primarily on the professional preparedness, motivation, and criminalistic-tactical competence of those who carry it out in practice. It is precisely for this reason that, within the framework of the international scientific research project "Confrontation in Criminalistic Theory and Practice" (Research Project No. 247), conducted at the Academy of the Police Force in Bratislava, a comprehensive empirical study was carried out aimed at comparing confrontation practice in the conditions of the Slovak Republic and the Czech Republic. The research was methodologically based on a questionnaire method, with respondents being investigators and authorised officers assigned to the areas of investigation and expedited investigation in both countries. The research aimed to verify four basic working hypotheses focused on the state of preparation for confrontation, the use of psychological knowledge, willingness to pursue further education, and the suitability of spatial conditions for conducting this act. All four hypotheses were confirmed by the research.⁸

The presented results aim to contribute to a deeper understanding of the state of confrontation practice in Slovakia and the Czech Republic, to identify its strengths, but above all to highlight the shortcomings that prevent the full utilisation of confrontation as a means of evidence in the investigative process. The research sample for the questionnaire method consisted of a total of 200 respondents. In the Slovak Republic, the sample comprised 100 respondents — 50 investigators and 50 authorised officers assigned to expedited investigation proceedings. An identical sample structure was applied in the Czech Republic, consisting of 50 investigators and 50 authorised officers. The questionnaires were distributed in paper form directly to the relevant departmental units. Prior to completing the questionnaires, an introductory interview was conducted within each respondent group in order to clarify the research objectives and the method of completion. Knowledge of these shortcomings is a necessary prerequisite for formulating specific criminalistic-tactical recommendations that could contribute to increasing the effectiveness of this demanding procedural act. The research results have been divided into 8 areas, namely:⁹

1. Practice and experience with conducting confrontation
2. Preparation for confrontation
3. Willingness to pursue education and attend professional courses
4. Use of psychology and criminalistic-tactical knowledge in practice
5. Types of questions and tactical procedures in confrontation
6. Expert assistance
7. Spatial conditions and the need for standardisation
8. Causes of false statements

1. Practice and Experience with Conducting Confrontation

Research conducted in the conditions of the Slovak Republic and the Czech Republic confirmed significant differences in the length of experience of persons conducting confrontation. In the Slovak Republic, the majority of investigators conduct confrontation with between 6 and 10 years of experience (49.50%), followed by investigators with 2 to 6 years of experience (32.75%), those with over 10 years of experience (9.75%), and those with under 2 years of experience at only 8%. In the area of expedited investigation, the group with under 2 years of experience dominates (33%), which signals that these officers are being assigned to conduct confrontation relatively early in their careers, despite it being one of the more

⁸ LACA, M., *Výsluch a konfrontácia v aplikačnej praxi*. s. 195-198.

⁹ LACA, M., *Výsluch a konfrontácia v aplikačnej praxi*. s. 129-194.

demanding procedural acts. In the Czech Republic, among authorised officers, those who have been conducting confrontation for 6 to 10 years predominate (45%), while investigators conduct confrontation predominantly with 2 to 6 years of experience (61%). An interesting comparative difference emerged in the question of the minimum length of experience required to handle the preparation and conduct of confrontation to a reasonably competent standard. Respondents in the Slovak Republic agreed overall, at 41%, on 2 years of experience, while investigators in the Slovak Republic consider 3 years of experience to be sufficient (40%) and authorised officers consider 2 years sufficient (44%).¹⁰

2. Preparation for Confrontation

One of the key findings of the research is the significant differences in the quality, scope, and systematic nature of preparation for conducting confrontation. Regarding the time devoted to preparation, investigators in the Slovak Republic predominantly prepare for confrontation within 0 to 0.5 hours (72.25%), with the overall assessment including authorised officers showing that as many as 45% of all respondents devote this short amount of time to preparation. This is followed by preparation lasting 0.5 to 1 hour (33%) and 1 to 3 hours (22%). A positive finding is that none of the respondents indicated that they do not prepare for confrontation at all (0 hours), which at least suggests that some form of preparation takes place. By contrast, in the Czech Republic, as many as 25.5% of all respondents devote 3 to 5 hours to preparation, which represents a striking difference compared to the Slovak Republic, where no preparation within this time range was recorded (0%). Regarding the specific manner of preparation, the situation differs significantly between investigators and authorised officers. Investigators in the Slovak Republic always or very often study all available materials and analyse them in 84.25% of cases, while authorised officers do so very often in 60% of cases. A detailed confrontation plan is always prepared by as many as 66.75% of investigators in the Slovak Republic, while in the area of expedited investigation only 14% of authorised officers always prepare a plan, with 32.5% preparing one only sometimes. There is also a marked difference in the preparation of a set of questions — investigators in the Slovak Republic always prepare a set of questions for the confronted persons in 78.25% of cases, while authorised officers do so always in only 36.75% of cases. These differences logically justify the need for internal standardisation of preparation procedures, which is reflected in the recommendations formulated in the final part of this study.¹¹

3. Willingness to Pursue Education and Attend Professional Courses

The research revealed a fundamental and concerning difference between Slovak and Czech practice in the area of willingness to pursue further education. In the Slovak Republic, as many as 58.63% of respondents do not feel the need to attend a course focused on confrontation tactics, 38.75% would welcome such an opportunity, and only 2.62% feel an active need to attend such a course. The situation in the Czech Republic is diametrically different — as many as 59.66% of respondents feel the need to attend a course focused on confrontation tactics, 30.84% do not feel this need, and only 9.5% would welcome such an opportunity. In the Slovak Republic, 71.25% of all respondents acquire new knowledge exclusively from their own practice, only 7.5% draw from current domestic criminalistic textbooks, 6.37% from conference proceedings and journal sources, 4.88% from foreign criminalistic textbooks, 4.63% from online sources, and only 5.37% through attendance at retraining courses. It is recommended to incorporate compulsory modules on confrontation tactics into both initial and continuous

¹⁰ LACA, M., *Výsluch a konfrontácia v aplikačnej praxi*. s. 133.

¹¹ LACA, M., *Výsluch a konfrontácia v aplikačnej praxi*. s. 139.

professional training of investigators and authorised officers. These modules should include practical exercises, case simulations, and instruction in the psychological aspects of conducting confrontation.¹²

4. Use of Psychology and Criminalistic-Tactical Knowledge in Practice

A particularly concerning finding — namely that police officers do not make sufficient use of knowledge from the psychological sciences¹³ and criminalistics when conducting confrontation — is the fact that in the Slovak Republic, as many as 92.38% of all respondents do not use psychological knowledge in their confrontation practice. Authorised officers do not use psychological knowledge in 98% of cases and investigators in 86.75%; only a minimal proportion indicated that they make use of knowledge of non-verbal communication. In the Czech Republic the situation is even more pronounced — 100% of respondents from both authorised officers and investigators do not use psychological knowledge in their confrontation practice. Regarding the methods used to detect false statements during confrontation, investigators in the Slovak Republic rely primarily on analysis of statements (43.75%) and observation of non-verbal communication cues (25.25%), while authorised officers rely on comparing the content of statements with other statements (37.25%) and their own intuition (33.5%). A significant comparative difference is also evident in this parameter — in the Czech Republic, comparison of statements with other statements dominates, in as many as 72.5% of cases. The fact that 33.5% of authorised officers in the Slovak Republic rely on their own intuition when detecting false statements points to insufficient methodological competence and the absence of systematic education in the field of criminalistic tactics. Such a low level of application of psychological knowledge clearly justifies the need for its systematic integration into training programmes and methodological guidelines for conducting confrontation.¹⁴

5. Types of Questions and Tactical Procedures in Confrontation

The research also focused on the types of questions respondents use when conducting confrontation. Among all question types, control questions dominate in the Slovak Republic (50.5% of respondents use them very often) and reminder questions (37% of respondents use them very often). Clarifying and specifying questions are used very often by 49.87% of respondents, while explanatory questions are used very often by only 24.63% of respondents. In the Slovak Republic, none of the respondents use captious questions (100% of responses: "I do not use them"). The results regarding suggestive questions are also encouraging — in the Slovak Republic, 97.25% of respondents do not use them, which again represents an improvement compared to 72.35%. In the Czech Republic, authorised officers predominantly make use of the statement of a confessing accused (77%), while investigators prefer analysis of the responses of the confronted persons (88%). Also of interest is the approach of both countries in situations where one of the confronted persons is giving a false statement: while in the Slovak Republic 35.5% of respondents require the person to repeat their claim directly to the other person's face and 34.88% argue the illogicality of the statement, in the Czech Republic as many as 89% of respondents allow the confronted person to continue giving a false statement and document it for further use. This difference reflects a distinct procedural culture and confrontation management strategy in the two countries. It appears appropriate to prioritise the establishment of purpose-built confrontation rooms equipped with suitable spatial layout, audio-visual recording technology, and a separate observation area. Although this measure is

¹² LACA, M., *Výsluch a konfrontácia v aplikačnej praxi*. s. 192.

¹³ METEŇKO, J., a kol. *Kriminalistická taktika*. s. 55-56.

¹⁴ LACA, M., *Výsluch a konfrontácia v aplikačnej praxi*. s. 136-137, 177-178.

financially and organisationally demanding, its benefits lie in enhanced procedural security, protection of vulnerable participants, and improved tactical options for the investigator.¹⁵

6. Expert Assistance

The research also focused on the availability of expert assistance in cases where an investigator or authorised officer requires consultation when preparing for confrontation. An experienced colleague in the Slovak Republic is always willing to provide expert assistance in 91.5% of cases. A superior officer in the Slovak Republic is willing to help always in only 0% of cases, but often in 56.5% of cases. The situation is significantly better in the Czech Republic, where a superior officer provides expert assistance always or very often in 97% of cases. A prosecutor provides virtually no expert assistance in the conduct of confrontation — in the Slovak Republic never in 84.25% of cases, and in the Czech Republic in as many as 100% of cases. This result points to the absence of systematic cooperation between the prosecution service and the police in the most demanding procedural acts.¹⁶

7. Spatial Conditions and the Need for Standardisation

The research confirmed the hypothesis regarding inadequate spatial conditions for conducting confrontation. Virtually all respondents (99.88% in the Slovak Republic and 100% in the Czech Republic) conduct confrontation in their own office, with none of the respondents using a dedicated room for the purpose. Nevertheless, 93.38% of all respondents in the Slovak Republic agreed that it is necessary to standardise the conditions for conducting confrontation, for example by establishing dedicated confrontation rooms. At the same time, as many as 83.37% of respondents indicate that such standardisation is realistically achievable. Regarding the question of the presence of a recording clerk during confrontation, 77.38% of respondents in the Slovak Republic answered affirmatively, which is consistent with criminalistic-tactical recommendations according to which the presence of a recording clerk enables the investigator to focus fully on conducting the confrontation. In the Czech Republic, 100% of respondents agreed that the presence of a recording clerk is appropriate and desirable during the conduct of confrontation. While the implementation of such facilities is constrained by financial and spatial limitations, the high level of agreement among respondents regarding the need for standardisation provides a realistic basis for the gradual introduction of purpose-built confrontation rooms.¹⁷

8. Causes of False Statements

A distinct area of the research concerned the most common causes of false statements in individual types of confrontation. In confrontation between a witness and an injured party in the Slovak Republic, fear of legal sanction dominates (51.75%), followed by unwillingness to testify (12.37%) and covering for co-perpetrators (12%). The situation in the Czech Republic differs — here, unwillingness to testify prevails (51.5%) and protection of a close person (27%), with fear of legal sanction appearing only in third place (10%).

In confrontation between a witness and the accused in the Slovak Republic, fear of legal sanction (39.25%) and protection of a close person (35.87%) dominate, while in the Czech Republic unwillingness to testify so as not to bring unnecessary difficulties upon oneself clearly prevails (70.5%).

In confrontation between co-accused in the Slovak Republic, the causes are distributed more evenly — fear of legal sanction ranks first (25.13%), followed by deficiencies in perception and memory (23.13%), protection of a close person (18.87%), and revenge, envy,

¹⁵ LACA, M., *Výsluch a konfrontácia v aplikačnej praxi*. s. 168-177.

¹⁶ LACA, M., *Výsluch a konfrontácia v aplikačnej praxi*. s. 149-155.

¹⁷ LACA, M., *Výsluch a konfrontácia v aplikačnej praxi*. s. 180-185.

or hatred (13.87%). These results are of exceptional value for criminalistic-tactical practice, as knowledge of the probable cause of a false statement enables the investigator to prepare a more targeted confrontation strategy.¹⁸

Based on the research findings presented in the preceding sections, the following criminalistic-tactical recommendations are proposed with the aim of increasing the effectiveness of confrontation as a means of evidence in investigative practice:

1. Standardisation of preparation procedures.

Authorised officers and investigators should adopt binding internal guidelines establishing a minimum standard for confrontation preparation, including mandatory review of all available case materials, preparation of a written confrontation plan, and formulation of a set of questions for each confronted person. The research findings indicate that the current absence of such standards leads to significant disparities in preparation quality, particularly between investigators and authorised officers.

2. Introduction of dedicated confrontation training. Given that 58.63% of respondents in the Slovak Republic do not feel the need for specialised training in confrontation tactics, and that knowledge is acquired predominantly through personal experience alone, it is recommended that compulsory modules on confrontation tactics be incorporated into the initial and continuous professional training of investigators and authorised officers. The curriculum should include practical exercises, case simulations, and instruction in the psychological aspects of confrontation conduct.

3. Integration of psychological knowledge into investigative practice. The finding that 92.38% of respondents in the Slovak Republic do not apply psychological knowledge during confrontation represents a critical deficit. It is recommended that training programmes systematically incorporate knowledge of non-verbal communication, stress indicators, and the psychology of testimony, enabling investigators to more reliably identify deceptive behaviour during confrontation.

4. Establishment of dedicated confrontation rooms. In view of the fact that virtually all confrontations are conducted in standard offices, and given that 93.38% of respondents in the Slovak Republic consider standardisation of spatial conditions necessary and 83.37% regard it as realistically achievable, it is recommended that police authorities prioritise the establishment of purpose-built confrontation rooms equipped with appropriate furniture layout, audio-visual recording equipment, and a separate observation area.

5. Systematic involvement of a recording clerk. Given that the presence of a recording clerk enables the investigator to devote full attention to directing the confrontation and observing the behaviour of the confronted persons, it is recommended that the assignment of a recording clerk be treated as a standard procedural requirement rather than an optional measure, in line with the practice already observed in the Czech Republic. In order to enable the investigator to focus fully on directing the confrontation and observing the behaviour of the confronted persons, the presence of a recording clerk should be regarded as a standard procedural requirement rather than an optional measure. The practice established in the Czech Republic represents a suitable model in this respect.

¹⁸ LACA, M., *Výsluch a konfrontácia v aplikačnej praxi*. s. 158-168.

6. Strengthening prosecutorial engagement. The finding that prosecutors provide no expert assistance during confrontation in 84.25% of cases in the Slovak Republic and in 100% of cases in the Czech Republic points to a systemic deficit in cooperation between the prosecution service and the police. It is recommended that formal mechanisms for pre-confrontation consultations between investigators and prosecutors be established, particularly in complex or high-profile cases.

7. Differentiated tactical approach based on the cause of false testimony. Investigators should be trained to identify the probable cause of a false statement prior to confrontation, primarily whether it is fear of legal sanction, protection of a close person, or deficiencies in perception and memory and to adapt their tactical approach accordingly. A targeted strategy tailored to the specific motivational profile of the confronted person is significantly more effective than a uniform approach.

8. Thinking through tactics prior to conducting confrontation. The finding that 42% of all respondents in the Slovak Republic never think through the tactics of confrontation in advance is unacceptable from a criminalistic-tactical standpoint. It is recommended that tactical preparation become a mandatory component of every preparatory process, with the investigator considering in advance the possible scenarios for the course of the confrontation, the reactions of the confronted persons, and the means of resolving any conflict situations that may arise.

9. Consideration of transferring the conduct of confrontation to the trial stage.

Résumé

The scientific study addresses confrontation as a means of evidence in criminal proceedings and is based on the results of international research conducted at the Academy of the Police Force in Bratislava. The author highlights in particular the importance of criminalistic-tactical procedures and compares the approaches of Slovakia and the Czech Republic, especially with regard to the preparation of investigators, the use of psychology, and the willingness to pursue further education.

From a historical perspective, confrontation in Slovak law long did not exist as an independent means of evidence and was understood merely as a component of examination. It is only the current legal regulation in § 125 of the Code of Criminal Procedure that grants it an independent status. At the same time, it remains an exceptional (subsidiary) instrument, employed only when fundamental discrepancies exist between statements and cannot be resolved by other means. The law also protects vulnerable persons, such as minors or victims of violent offences, in respect of whom confrontation is restricted or entirely excluded.

From a practical standpoint, this is a relatively demanding act that requires thorough preparation, active direction by the investigator, and the ability to perceive the non-verbal expressions of the confronted persons. The research, however, revealed that Slovak practice has considerable room for improvement in precisely this area. Preparation is often brief and unsystematic, with many investigators failing to think through the tactics of conducting confrontation in advance. Moreover, psychological knowledge is utilised only minimally, which can significantly reduce the effectiveness of the entire act. The comparison with the Czech Republic revealed interesting differences. Czech investigators devote more time to preparation, perceive the demands of confrontation more realistically, and show greater interest in further professional education. In Slovakia, by contrast, there is a noticeable decline in interest in education and a strong orientation toward gaining experience directly from practice. Differences also emerged in the actual approach to confrontation. Slovak investigators tend to respond actively to false statements and attempt to challenge them directly, while Czech

investigators are more inclined to allow the person to testify and subsequently use the statement as evidence. The physical conditions also present a problem - confrontations are most commonly conducted in standard offices without specially adapted facilities. Overall, the study shows that while the legal regulation of confrontation in Slovakia is adequate, its practical application encounters several problems. These relate in particular to insufficient preparation, weak utilisation of psychological knowledge, and a low level of systematic education. The author therefore highlights the need to improve the professional training of investigators, create better conditions for conducting confrontation, and strengthen their criminalistic-tactical skills.

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